

Professional Training of Future Primary School Teachers Based on Kazakh National Identity

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Abstract: The purpose of the research is to develop a model of future primary school teacher training based on the traditions of the Kazakh people. The practical results of the research are that the article is focused on developing professional training for future primary school teachers based on the ethnopsychological and ethnopedagogical traditions of the Kazakh people. The results and the proposed model can be used in forming primary school teachers' professional training and developing their professional competencies in modern conditions, considering the ethnopsychological and ethnopedagogical aspects of vocational training.

Anahtar Sözcükler:

İlköğretim,
mesleki eğitim,
Kazak kimliği,
mesleki yeterlik

Kazak Ulusal Kimliği Temelinde İlköğretim Öğretmenlerinin Mesleki Gelişimi

Özet: Araştırmanın amacı, Kazak halkının geleneklerine dayalı olarak geleceğin ilkököl öğretmeni yetiştirme modelini geliştirmektir. Araştırmanın pratik sonuçları, makalenin, Kazak halkının etnopsikolojik ve etnopedagojik geleneklerine dayalı olarak geleceğin ilkököl öğretmenlerine yönelik mesleki eğitimin geliştirilmesine odaklandığıdır. Sonuçlar ve önerilen model, mesleki eğitimin etnopsikolojik ve etnopedagojik yönleri dikkate alınarak, ilkököl öğretmenlerinin mesleki eğitimlerinin oluşturulmasında ve mesleki yeterliliklerinin modern koşullarda geliştirilmesinde kullanılabilir.

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1. Introduction

The modernization of professional training of pedagogical staff in the Republic of Kazakhstan rapidly changed during the transition to 12 years of education. It is connected with the rapid development of information technologies and the enhancement of technical means in the education process, which is accompanied by the needs of schoolchildren (Orakova et al., 2024). In this connection, the importance of the research is developing the model of primary school teachers based on ethnopsychological features and ethnopedagogical traditions.

The quality improvement in training competitive and highly qualified school teachers depends on creating professional training conditions (Aubakirova et al., 2024). In the present research, they are considered teachers for modern schools who are able to organize conditions for primary education in the country by taking into account traditional norms and vocational training. Launched in the 2011-2020 school year, the state program implementation for developing the education system in the Republic of Kazakhstan aimed to ensure the formation of professionally competent individuals. The competitive specialists are considered capable of solving professional tasks independently and creatively, understanding the personal and social significance of the professional activity, and being responsible for its results, so an effective supply management system will be created. From this, it can be seen that the concept of “competence” has become a key term used in education and specialist training (Abdiyev et al., 2023; Turgumbayeva et al., 2023).

Uzakbaeva and Zholdasbekova (2015) wrote that the model should be based on the need to modernise future teachers' vocational training system concerning the challenges of training competitive specialists. Therefore, it should be based on the formation of the teacher's needs in a conscious, skilled orientation in the broadest social professional field. It is focused on developing a taste for exploration, selection of subject content, forms and methods of teaching and education, issues of pedagogical creativity, and modern pedagogical realities.

Updating the structure of training primary school teachers and modelling the mechanism of its efficiency and dynamic functioning can be carried out according to how it contributes to forming a competitive personality in his speciality. Supporting new ideas based on the enhancement of national education mainly depends on the quality of the pedagogical staff (Zimnyaya, 2012). Hence, the term professional competence is currently used to define the awareness, skills, and abilities of the personality, which is a special field. Professional competence is essential for specialists to gain during the course of study. Therefore, it is essential to form the so-called subject competencies at different levels of learning. They are based on future specialists' needs, especially at the pre-profile and core stages of their training preparation.

In modern educational programs, the term “competence” is usually used in connection with the owner of a certain social and professional status and is characterized by the compatibility of understanding, knowledge, and skills in performing the work with the solution of the problem to be performed at the specific level.

Professional competencies of future primary school teachers include different communicative competencies and abilities when they face the objectives of the lesson and the whole organization process. They need cognitive, social, and communicative competence, research, and organizational competencies. Professional competence defines a certain education level and experiences sufficient to successfully perform a future primary

school teacher's particular social or substantive functions. In our positions, they also need to take into account ethnopsychological features and ethnopedagogical traditions of Kazakh schools. The importance of this research is that we define a future primary school teacher's professional competence from the points of view of modern approaches in the context of the modern education system.

2. Literature Review

In developing a future primary school teacher's professional competences, communicative learning skills, skills in organizing educational and cognitive activities, and practical application of their knowledge in special fields play a systematic role. In higher institutions, the educational programs focus on the development of their professional competencies (Abdiyev et al., 2023). A competence-based approach to the organization of training a future primary school teacher in profiled schools is aimed at shaping his readiness for organization and working in a primary school. This process requires an emphasis on mastering a set of competences as: general personal, cultural, communicative, cognitive, informational, social, professional, and interpersonal competencies.

Nowadays, it cannot be ignored the influence of the e-learning environment on teaching any subject. E-learning and digital resources have become part of teaching (Kilinc et al., 2023; Yussupova et al., 2023). Provorova et al. (2020) believe that "the percentage of students will grow and e-learning will be gradually transformed from the auxiliary form into the main one" in the course of teaching. All the teaching processes should focus on the development of students' abilities, skills, and competencies in educational programs.

According to Norris (1991), presenting different types of crucial and professional competencies is essential. Fundamental competencies are universal ones applied in various situations in their social life. Professional competencies include:

1. *Informational competence* - readiness for working with information by using paper and electronic means.
2. *Communicative competence* - readiness for communication with other people in the professional field.
3. *Cooperative competence* - willingness to cooperate with other people, staff members, schoolchildren, parents, etc.
4. *Problem-solving competence* - readiness for solving problems and problem situations in the educational field.

Scholars usually focus on the importance of communicative competence (Karimova et al., 2023). Abdukadirova et al. (2020) consider critical competence in teaching as communicative competence, as it deals with developing all meta-language skills. Torres-Gordillo et al. (2020) also define 'communicative competence' as something that should be developed in teacher training. Orazbayeva (2000) underlines that the most critical part of teacher training is the development of critical competencies: research, methodological, organizational, self-education, and prognostic competencies.

Nagymzhanova (2003) says that the basis of pedagogical education is the professional training of teachers. A professional teacher should have a good command of the methodology and be able to use the educational tool to develop individuals purposefully. In order to creatively solve complex work, it is necessary to train future specialists to be able to combine their technical thinking ability with action correctly and to accept it consciously.

According to Rubinstein (1940) and Vygotsky (1980), the fundamentals of teaching at school are based on the norms of general psychology. The future teacher's professional quality and personal ability are directed to the creative activities and performance of teaching, developing, and educating the future generation. Kazakh ethnopsychological features are always at the centre of teaching principles for a primary school teacher.

Eliseeva and Ersarina (2019) consider that the development of a primary school program involves selecting and using individual methods and approaches for each child based on his individual characteristics and capabilities. Each specialist decides which areas to work on and which methods and approaches to use based on individual research. The specialist should know and master modern and innovative psychological-pedagogical technologies (special and alternative methods) to choose the appropriate methods of psychological-pedagogical work to ensure the effectiveness of his work with the child. He needs literary sources of methodological guides on pedagogics and psychology, which show various specialists' educational and methodological literature.

We should integrate traditional teaching methods with modern technologies and digital education tools in this connection. Osova et al. (2021) stated that "digital technologies greatly contribute to high-quality teacher training and the effective formation of future primary school teachers' competencies". In this connection, we consider technical competence to be the core of the model of all modern teaching staff, as they use digital technologies in their everyday activities (Yeleussiz, 2024).

Demyanenko and Leyfa (2019) also consider that digital educational space is understood as "technical and educational-methodical support, a system-organized set of information, presented in digital forms that include digital information and digital educational resources, a set of digital information and telecommunication technologies and tools for ensuring the development of educational programs regardless of the location of students".

Therefore, the teacher's professional-pedagogical training is based on the social-political, general scientific, special, psychological-pedagogical and professional-methodical education system, and we understand that the combined formation of these qualities is the teacher's ability to perform professional activities (Tolen et al., 2023). Apart from all these components, some core components are related to vocational training.

Turkestanova et al. (2023) consider the formation of future primary school teachers' professional competence; we need to consider the specifics of native culture and language. Also, Vesnin (1998) distinguishes four types of professional competence:

1. functionality that describes and implements professional knowledge and business skills;
2. intellectuality, which is reflected in the ability to think analytically and implement a complex basis for fulfilling one's duties;
3. allowing to act in appropriate situations - situational;
4. social, which assumes the presence of communicative and integrative abilities.

In our opinion, the formation of all types of professional competences is a leading role for teachers of higher educational institutions. In conclusion, today, the competence-based approach in education is modern which regulates the major goals of the educational process by forming future specialists' professional competencies.

3. Method

The resulting reliability is proven by the theoretical analysis of the methodology model and the analysis of advanced pedagogical experience. The empirical research methods and methodology of quantitative and qualitative analysis of the control assessment were obtained to prove the main purpose and objectives. The modelling method was used to develop the content of the elective course ‘Primary school pedagogics’ and key competencies on forming future specialists’ professional competencies.

The research methodology was carried out in 3 stages (diagnostic, formative and concluding) during one semester (4 months) from 28.02.2023-15.05.2023 at Korkyt Ata Kyzylorda University. The two groups of specialty “primary school teachers” were chosen for the experiment: the experimental group (n=20: EG) and the control group (n=20: CG). The participants of the experimental research are 3-year students who are future primary school teachers.

Table 1.
Stages of experiment

Stages	Content	CG	Percentage %
<i>Stage I: Diagnostic stage</i>	Setting the aim of experimental pedagogical work, planning vocational and pilot experiments. The research problem was generalized and analyzed based on the model of future primary school teachers’ professional competence, the logic of the research methodology was formulated, and the methodology of the experiment model was developed.	20+20	50+50
<i>Stage II: Formative stage</i>	The course program for target groups was conducted based on Kazakh ethnopsychological features and ethnopedagogical traditions according to the chosen technology and model. The course program topics, case tasks, and a set of exercises for the formation of professional competence of the target group were organized.	20+20	50+50
<i>Stage III: Concluding stage</i>	The formative and summative assessments were used systematically to summarize the experimental data analysis, and the main conclusions of the research were formulated.	20+20	50+50
	Total	40	100

The statistical data analysis during the experiment helped determine the future primary school teachers’ professional competence based on Kazakh ethnopsychological features, ethnopedagogical traditions development, and the experimental stages developed by the authors.

3.1. Experimental Process

The lack of time in teaching, taking into account the limited psychological and physiological capabilities of students, allows them to systematically carry out appropriate activities following the high level of educational work; that is, by increasing the pace of teaching, it is necessary first to bring students’ knowledge to the basic level and further develop it. The following are the main directions for strengthening the teaching pace:

Figure 1. Model on the formation of future primary school teachers' professional competence based on ethnopsychological features and ethnopedagogical traditions

1. the technology of rational and systematic placement of subjects to be studied in a given specialty within the planned period of time (modular, thematic, chapter, departmental organization of the educational process);
2. considering the capabilities and abilities of each student from the beginning when designing the educational process (new technology of education);
3. taking into account the capabilities and abilities of each student at each stage of the didactic module (in the initial, middle, and final stages);
4. use of the method of intensive monitoring when predicting and evaluating the student's level of education;
5. to increase the pace of teaching activities, to form purposeful habituation to general educational activities and to study what we teach, how we teach, and what we teach with define the goals that point to the "conditional" direction.

Pedagogical technology is rigorous scientific planning and, more precisely, imagination, ensuring pedagogical activity's success. The task of specialists is to consider the child's needs and create favorable conditions for overcoming learning difficulties and development. The teacher has to use personal orientation and an individual approach: accepting the child as an active person with his own needs and motivations and personal resources for development, not only based on his problems and disorders. When creating the program, consider the child's weaknesses and strengths based on his interests and psychological character.

In order to ensure the purposeful formation of technological (methodical) training for future primary school teachers, we have established the purpose and tasks of monitoring each educational result. The knowledge and skills that can be formed during the monitoring of each study result were determined, and the change of the results at the level of training of future primary school teachers was considered. Many scholars, like Ayapbergenova *et al.* (2021), stated that the assessment of the development level of future primary school teachers' special competencies at the universities carried out special programs and results of the teaching process.

Before experimenting, we created a model of primary school teachers based on ethnopsychological features and ethnopedagogical traditions. It consists of three blocks: basic theoretical and methodological block, content-procedural and resulting (Figure 1). As we see in Figure 1, the content component of the methodological model of professional training is based on ethnopsychological features and ethnopedagogical traditions.

The results and sub-competences are: subject, communicative, cognitive-educational and ethno-cultural competencies. They are all key and essential competencies for future primary school teachers. Subject competence is a set of knowledge, qualifications, skills and qualities of activities related to certain disciplines in educational activities. It includes the ability to apply the basics of pedagogical and social psychology (source: <https://www.tarbie.kz/25368>). Communicative competence helps to solve several important tasks; it enables productive interaction, including dialogue with representatives of different nationalities who hold other views and directions, to implement conflict resolutions and to establish relationships with people in different positions in a group to achieve an expected result (Temirgalinova, 2022).

Cognitive-educational competence is critical, as cognition is a philosophical category of the socio-historical process that forms the information of a personality, which determines the purpose and motivation of an action. Cognitive-educational competence helps to understand the emotional content or the condition of things to find the truth of the objective world. It is developed through the creative activity of the subject to acquire real knowledge about the world, and it is presented in terms of obtaining information about the external environment (Zimnyaya, 2012)

Ethnocultural competence reflects readiness for inter-ethnic mutual understanding and interaction based on the knowledge acquired about the ethnic culture of one's own nation and other nations in everyday life and educational classes. The formation of ethno-cultural competence aims at the integration of knowledge from various sources and the ability to solve problems of inter-ethnic interaction, assimilation of students into their native culture, and then into another culture. By comparing the value of one's own culture with other values, recognition creates an opportunity to enter another person's culture to develop inter-ethnic understanding and dialogue (Poshtareva, 2005).

The theoretical and methodological block consists of approaches and principles of teaching. The content-procedural block has the following components: methods and means of achieving the teaching goal, types of lessons, technologies, and system of knowledge about the effectiveness of the teaching-educational process. The resulting block is based on two main criteria: a future specialist's subject and ethno-cultural competence.

4. Findings and Discussion

Standardizing the pedagogical technology, we divide the technology according to the type of organization of the relationship between the teacher and the student: self-learning, stationary training in the joint activity of the student and the teacher, extracurricular, the number of interacting hours students with the teacher (individual and group work). The specificity of the methodology depends on the composition of the infrastructure elements used. For example, the value of modern technology in teaching, using conversations and solving professional tasks is determined.

We conducted our experiment's lessons in three stages (diagnostic, formative and concluding) during one semester (4 months) at Korkyt Ata Kyzylorda University. The two groups of 3-year students of "Primary school teachers" were chosen for our experiment: EG (n=20) and CG (n=20). The stages of our experiment are described in Table 1. The experiment aims to verify the created model's effectiveness in forming future primary school teachers' professional competence based on Kazakh ethnopsychological features and ethnopedagogical traditions.

At the diagnostic stage of experimental work, the monitoring of the teaching process identified the students' cognitive motives in the field of their professional needs. The formative stage of experimental work was the organized formation of professional training using an elective course following the model of our methodology (Figure 1). Students participated in case tasks during the lessons and responded to professional questions. We widely used integrated technologies in the experimental group using ethno-cultural texts and resources, while in the control group, we mostly used traditional methods. This stage aims to familiarize students with the purpose of preliminary training through specially designed teaching tools, to draw attention to what problems and questions during the study, why it is necessary to study this thing, and the practical value and significance of the ethno-cultural material being taught. In the course of the first and second stages, the following objectives were set:

- to analyze the special program on training primary school teachers;
- to conduct a selection of material for experiential learning;
- to organize a practical course of language drill;
- to develop instructions and guidelines.

Using the course “Pedagogy and Methodology of Primary Education” among the experimental group students made it possible to systematize knowledge and skills in educational programs in the direction of professional training. Under the standard of higher professional education and work curriculum, the following types of educational work were carried out with students:

- on the organization of educational processes (lecture, seminar/practical);
- organization of students’ independent work and student’s independent work (activities) performed under the guidance of the teacher;
- forms of organization of individual, group and collective training;
- work with literature for training future primary school teachers and teaching subjects in primary school;
- identification and analysis of educational materials that form knowledge in the content aspect of primary school education;
- modeling pedagogical technologies’ implementation in teaching students, etc. (please see Table 2 for the course program and its content).

Table 2.

The content of the course Pedagogy and methodology of primary education

Topics of Lectures	Topics for seminar discussion
Model 1: Professional self-awareness and teacher development	
1 The system of primary education	Working with teaching programs
2 Professional timelines of FL teachers	Professional timelines Teaching methods and resources
3 Advantages of teaching resources	
Model 2: Theory and methodology of educational work in primary school	
4 Professional timelines	Classroom management; Tips for traditional teaching;
5 Lesson planning for primary schoolchildren	
Model 3: Teaching approaches and materials	
6 Selection of teaching materials	Traditional methods: communicative methods
7 Approaches at primary schools of Kazakhstan	Innovational methods: ICT Teaching technologies of digital education
8 Competence-based approach	
Model 4: Psychological-pedagogical bases of teaching and primary education	
9 Primary education system of KZ	
10 Travelling and studying abroad	Exchange of professional experience; Teaching Kazakh culture and traditions: places of interest
11 Internship for school teachers	“Workbook” and “Monitoring diary” work methodology
12 Psychology of primary school children	
Model 4: Ethno-cultural aspect of primary education	
13 General scientific methods and principles of teaching methodology of world studies	Kazakh culture vs other countries; Tasks of teaching methodology of world studies
14 Extracurricular work on “Methodology of teaching the subject of world studies”. The organization of subject	Presentation research topics for scientific conferences. Model program on the subject “World Studies” for grades 1-4 of primary education
15 “Methodology of teaching the subject of world studies”.	

According to the complexity and nature of the educational materials, teaching conditions can be created in one or more ways according to the proposed methodological system, and the following are included in the constituent elements of case tasks: “Teaching conditions” created based on the cognitive and action theory of the learning process:

1. Learning goal;
2. Topics (directions) of the lesson;
3. Time management;
4. All teacher (teacher) activities during the lesson (including acquiring knowledge and forming professional competence).
5. All activities of the students in gaining knowledge.
6. Technical means of training are used in the teaching process.
7. Technological tools of teaching are used in the teaching process.

The program consists of discussion topics, teaching resources, and teacher activities to create a model of students’ activities. For this, the teacher considers the materials and materialized technological processes of students’ actions. The cognitive and communicative methods using digital resources for training: developing a model for working with text using case tasks, exercises for forming cognitive, communicative competence and creativity. If the activity being taught is combined with an activity outside of thought activity, then such an activity is material, and if the action is carried out with the help of any image, schemes, such an action can be called materialized.

Achievement of educational activities in accordance with the goals of educational cycles fully reveals the meaning of the concept of educational technology and is aimed at solving the problem of “How to effectively teach?”. During the formative stage, the following tasks were set to

- conduct training for lectures and seminar lessons, and work out methodical recommendations based on the results,
- preparation of students for primary education is carried out using special topics for discussion and teaching materials.

We widely used digital resources that helped compensate for the lack of communicative situations in exchanging professional and academic experiences. We focused on the idea of Alawamleh et al. (2020), who stated that effective communication occurs when a desired effect results from intentional information exchange. It is the communication between different individuals that is performed in a desired manner.

In our experiment’s concluding stage, we tested students’ knowledge using pre and post-tests. We prepared pre and post-tests to evaluate the future primary school teachers’ professional competencies according to 4 criteria: students’ ethno-cultural competence, development of cognitive competence through case tasks and activities, and communicative and ethno-cultural competence in discussion of lesson topics. The monitoring and assessment of students’ activities were also evaluated through individual tasks and participation in discussions during the semester. The students of two groups (EG and CG) participated in the tests. The pre-test results in EG and CG are an average of 84%. The indicators are the same according to our criteria at the beginning of the diagnostic stage (Figure 2). In the indicators of the pre-test, we do not see significant differences at the diagnostic stage.

Figure 2. Pre-experimental indicators of students' professional competence

According to our model, we conducted elective courses for EG and CG students. Both groups took part in the lectures and seminar classes, during which the program content was carried out equally. The only change was we mostly used case tasks and individual tasks using integrated technologies for EG group. Changes recorded in the post-experiment test based on the teacher's assessment and the students' subject competence, cognitive competence, communicative competence and ethno-cultural competence are accidentally higher from EG students for 5% and 7% levels than EG students (Figure 3). Figure 3 shows that the EG level in all four criteria gradually increased to approximately 91%. The post-test results showed higher efficiency in forming the EG group students' professional competence than CG.

Figure 3. Indication of students' professional competence at the post-experimental stage (in CC group and EC group)

The results prove that the model and a course program created to improve students' professional competence showed their efficiency. According to the results of the presented experimental work, the professional communication level increased significantly from a lower to a higher average in EG. The effectiveness of the methodology established by the authors is confirmed in the course of program implementation. Based on the above, as a methodological conclusion of the organization of the teaching process, the creation of a unified teaching technology is taking place as an objective law of the development of the organization of the educational process. In other words, the mentioned model is not a system that will take place by itself. Its effectiveness in the teaching process promotes a number of positions:

1. each training component should be highly connected;
2. in the process of knowledge acquisition, strict observance of the stages of knowledge acquisition and their sequence;
3. the effectiveness of the system in the educational process should take place in its unity in all cases.

In conclusion, it can be said that the research work results established that the goal was achieved and the case tasks were solved. The use of ethno-cultural materials and research topics has led to an increase in students' professional competence.

5. Conclusion

The organization of the teaching process based on the competence-based approach makes it possible to impart professional competence in the educational process. Based on conducted research on the future primary school teachers' professional competence development, a methodological basis has been developed as a model for special courses. The model created for forming future primary school teachers' professional competence is based on Kazakh ethnopsychological features and ethnopedagogical traditions.

1. Professional competence formation aims to develop cognitive, communicative, and ethno-cultural competencies.
2. The model of professional competence is considered a tool for designing special programs based on the basic content of teacher training, creating the special programs and carrying out the training process.
3. The two forms of testing have undergone the manifestation of the main components of professional competence. The most critical conditions for the model implementation are integrating modern technologies and methodological support for using ethno-cultural materials in vocational training.

Note on Ethical Issues

The authors confirm that the study does not need ethics committee approval according to the research integrity rules in their country (Date of Confirmation: 15/04/2024).

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